

Way the oxidation state change with the velocity of electromagnetic waves

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Abstract

In this paper oxidation and reduction reactions were studied. Oxidation is loss of the electrons and increases the oxidation state or the oxidation number. The reduction gains of the electrons and decreases the oxidation number and increases the reduction number. This paper shows the law of the oxidation state change with the velocity of electromagnetic waves. Also, the paper gives the law of the oxidation number and reduction number changes with the length of electromagnetic waves. The transition function of the oxidation state was established. These laws are announced the first time in the literature.

Keywords: *oxidation state, oxidants, reductants, electrons transfer, redox reaction.*

1. Introduction

Atoms are the basic particles of the chemical elements. An atom consists of a nucleus of protons and generally neutrons, surrounded by an electromagnetically bound swarm of electrons. The chemical elements are distinguished from each other by the number of protons that are in their atoms. For example, any atom that contains 11 protons is sodium, and any atom that contains 29 protons is copper. Atoms with the same number of protons but a different number of neutrons are called isotopes of the same element.

Atoms are extremely small, typically around 100 picometers across. A human hair is about a million carbon atoms wide. Atoms are smaller than the shortest wavelength of visible light, which means humans cannot see atoms with conventional microscopes. They are so small that accurately predicting their behavior using classical physics is not possible due to quantum effects.

More than 99.9994% of an atom's mass is in the nucleus. Protons have a positive electric charge and neutrons have no charge, so the nucleus is positively charged. The electrons are negatively charged, and this opposing charge is what binds them to the nucleus. If the numbers of protons and electrons are equal, as they normally are, then the atom is electrically neutral as a whole. If an atom has more electrons than protons, then it has an overall negative charge, and is called a negative ion (or anion). Conversely, if it has more protons than electrons, it has a positive charge, and is called a positive ion (or cation) [1].

2. Oxidation and reduction reactions

Redox (*/ˈrɛdɒks/ RED-oks, /ˈriːdɒks/ REE-doks*, reduction–oxidation or oxidation–reduction) is a type of chemical reaction in which the oxidation states of the reactants change [1]-[5]. Oxidation is the loss of electrons or an increase in the oxidation state, while reduction is the gain of electrons or a decrease in the oxidation state. The oxidation and reduction processes occur simultaneously in the chemical reaction.

There are two classes of redox reactions, electron-transfer – only one (usually) electron flows from the atom, ion, or molecule being oxidized to the atom, ion, or molecule that is reduced. This type of redox reaction is often discussed in terms of redox couples and electrode potentials.

Atom transfer – an atom transfers from one substrate to another. For example, in the rusting of iron, the oxidation state of iron atoms increases as the iron converts to an oxide, and simultaneously, the oxidation state of oxygen decreases as it accepts electrons released by the iron. Although oxidation reactions are commonly associated with forming oxides, other chemical species can serve the same function [6]-[7]. In hydrogenation, bonds like C=C are reduced by transfer of hydrogen atoms.

"Redox" is a portmanteau of the words "REDuction" and "OXidation." The term "redox" was first used in 1928.

Oxidation is a process in which a substance loses electrons. Reduction is a process in which a substance gains electrons. The processes of oxidation and reduction occur simultaneously and cannot occur independently. Thus, in the reaction, the reductant or reducing agent loses electrons and is oxidized, and the oxidant or oxidizing agent gains electrons and is reduced. The pair of an oxidizing and reducing agent that is involved in a particular reaction is called a redox pair. A redox couple is a reducing species and its corresponding oxidizing form, e.g., $\text{Fe}^{2+} / \text{Fe}^{3+}$. The oxidation alone and the reduction alone are each called a *half-reaction* because two half-reactions always occur together to form a whole reaction [8].

In electrochemical reactions the oxidation and reduction processes do occur simultaneously but are separated in space.

2.1 Oxidants

Oxidation originally implied a reaction with oxygen to form an oxide. Later, the term was expanded to encompass substances that accomplished chemical reactions similar to those of oxygen. Ultimately, the meaning was generalized to include all processes involving the loss of electrons or the increase in the oxidation state of a chemical species [8]. Substances that have the ability to oxidize other substances (cause them to lose electrons) are said to be oxidative or oxidizing, and are known as oxidizing agents, oxidants, or oxidizers. The oxidant removes electrons from another substance, and is thus itself reduced. Because it "accepts" electrons, the oxidizing agent is also called an electron acceptor. Oxidants are usually chemical substances with elements in high oxidation states (e.g., N_2O_4 , MnO_4^- , CrO_3 , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$, OsO_4), or else highly electronegative elements (e.g. O_2 , F_2 , Cl_2 , Br_2 , I_2) that can gain extra electrons by oxidizing another substance.

Oxidizers are oxidants, but the term is mainly reserved for sources of oxygen, particularly in the context of explosions. Nitric acid is a strong oxidizer [9].

2.2 Reductants

Substances that have the ability to reduce other substances (cause them to gain electrons) are said to be reductive or reducing and are known as reducing agents, reductants, or reducers. The reductant transfers electrons to another substance and is thus itself oxidized [4]. Because it donates electrons, the reducing agent is also called an electron donor. Electron donors can also form charge transfer complexes with electron acceptors. The word reduction originally referred to the loss in weight upon heating a metallic ore such as a metal oxide to extract the metal. In other words, ore was "reduced" to metal. Antoine Lavoisier demonstrated that this loss of weight was due to the loss of oxygen as a gas. Later, scientists realized that the metal atom gains electrons in this process. The meaning of reduction then became generalized to include all processes involving a gain of electrons [8]. Reducing equivalent refers to chemical species which transfer the equivalent of one electron in redox reactions. The term is common in biochemistry [5]. A reducing equivalent can be an electron or a hydrogen atom as a hydride ion.

Reductants in chemistry are very diverse. Electropositive elemental metals, such as lithium, sodium, magnesium, iron, zinc, and aluminium, are good reducing agents. These metals donate electrons relatively readily.

Hydride transfer reagents, such as NaBH_4 and LiAlH_4 , reduce by atom transfer: they transfer the equivalent of hydride or H^- . These reagents are widely used in the reduction of carbonyl compounds to alcohols. A related method of reduction involves the use of hydrogen gas (H_2) as sources of H atoms [4].

3. The oxidation state of atom

The oxidation state definition an alternative modern description is: the number of hydrogen atoms that can combine with an element in a binary hydride or twice the number of oxygen atoms combining with an element in its oxide or oxides.

This definition differs from the IUPAC definition as an element can be said to have more than one valence.

Because of the ambiguity of the term valence, other notations are currently preferred. Beside the lambda notation, as used in the IUPAC nomenclature of inorganic chemistry, oxidation state is a more clear indication of the electronic state of atoms in a molecule [9].

The oxidation state of an atom in a molecule gives the number of valence electrons it has gained or lost. In contrast to the valence number, the oxidation state can be positive (for an electropositive atom) or negative (for an electronegative atom).

The electrons of an atom are attracted to the protons in an atomic nucleus by the electromagnetic force. The protons and neutrons in the nucleus are attracted to each other by the nuclear force [10]-[13]. This force is usually stronger than the electromagnetic force that repels the positively charged protons from one another. Under certain circumstances, the repelling electromagnetic force becomes stronger than the nuclear force. In this case, the nucleus splits and leaves behind different elements. This is a form of nuclear decay.

Atoms can attach to one or more other atoms by chemical bonds to form chemical compounds such as molecules or crystals. The ability of atoms to attach and detach from each other is responsible for most of the physical changes observed in nature.

The oxidation state of an atom in a molecule is the number of valence electrons, but the oxidation state can be positive or negative. For example, in acetylene, $C \equiv C$, each carbon atom is valence 4, but it has oxidation state -1 [9].

Oxidation state is increased in processes involving the loss of electrons.

If n_e is smaller then n_{OX} is greater. (1)

If n_e is greater then n_{OX} is smaller. (2)

Let consider the electromagnetic waves of a reaction.

Speed of electromagnetic waves can be defined as in equation (3) as product of frequency and wavelength:

$$v = f\lambda \quad (3)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{v}{f} \quad (4)$$

When atom, ion, begin to change wavelength then the oxidative state is changed. Wavelength during quant energy radiation has not to be constant. If wavelength become longer is greater probability to lose electron and oxidation state increases. If wavelength become shorter is less probability loss electron and oxidation state decreases.

If λ is longer then n_{OX} is greater.

If λ is shorter then n_{OX} is smaller. (6)

In the transition oxidation state can defined as:

$$n_{OX} = \theta(\lambda) \quad (7)$$

As the similar manner for reduction state can conclude:

If λ is shorter then n_{RED} is smaller. (8)

If λ is longer then n_{RED} is greater. (9)

Redox number can be defined as:

$$\text{Redox} = \frac{n_{RED}}{n_{OX}} \quad (10)$$

where n_e - electron, n_{OX} -oxidation number, v velocity of electromagnetic wave (quant), λ wavelength, f - frequency, n_{RED} - reduction number.

The law of the oxidation state of atom dependence of the electromagnetic waves velocity was derived the first time in the literature.

In this paper the law of oxidation state chainging with length of electromegnetic wave was derived first time in the literature.

The law of the oxidation number and reduction number changes with the length of electromagnetic waves was derived the first time in this paper, in refers to the literature.

The transision function of the oxidation state has defined by equation (7).

4. Rates, mechanisms, and energies

Redox reactions can occur slowly, as in the formation of rust, or rapidly, as in the case of burning fuel. Electron transfer reactions are generally fast, occurring within the time of mixing.

The mechanisms of atom-transfer reactions are highly variable because many kinds of atoms can be transferred. Such reactions can also be quite complex, involving many steps. The mechanisms of electron-transfer reactions occur by two distinct pathways, inner sphere electron transfer and outer sphere electron transfer.

Analysis of bond energies and ionization energies in water allows calculation of the thermodynamic aspects of redox reactions.

4.1 Redox reactions in biology

Many essential biological processes involve redox reactions. Before some of these processes can begin, iron must be assimilated from the environment [5], [6], [14].

Cellular respiration, for instance, is the oxidation of glucose $C_6H_{12}O_6 + 6 O_2$ and the reduction of oxygen to water. The summary equation for cellular respiration is:

The rate of reaction respiration can define as:

$$\frac{dc_A}{dt} = \frac{dc_B}{dt} = -kc_A \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{dc_C}{dt} = kc_A \quad (13)$$

where c - concentration, mol / m^3 and k - the specific rate constant, s^{-1} , t - time, s

The process of cellular respiration also depends heavily on the reduction of NAD^+ to $NADH$ and the reverse reaction (the oxidation of $NADH$ to NAD^+). Photosynthesis and cellular respiration are complementary, but photosynthesis is not the reverse of the redox reaction in cellular respiration:

Enzymatic browning is an example of a redox reaction that takes place in most fruits and vegetables (Fig.1).

Biological energy is frequently stored and released using redox reactions. Photosynthesis involves the reduction of carbon dioxide into sugars and the oxidation of water into molecular oxygen. The reverse reaction, respiration, oxidizes sugars to produce carbon dioxide and water. As intermediate steps, the reduced carbon compounds are used to reduce nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD^+) to $NADH$, which then contributes to the creation of a proton gradient, which drives the synthesis of adenosine triphosphate (ATP) and is maintained by the reduction of oxygen. In animal cells, mitochondria perform similar functions.

Fig. 1 The glucose

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sugars to produce carbon dioxide and water. As intermediate steps, the reduced carbon compounds are used to reduce nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD⁺) to NADH, which then contributes to the creation of a proton gradient, which drives the synthesis of adenosine triphosphate (ATP) and is maintained by the reduction of oxygen. In animal cells, mitochondria perform similar functions.

The term *redox state* is often used to describe the balance of GSH/GSSG, NAD⁺/NADH and NADP⁺/NADPH in a biological system such as a cell or organ. The redox state is reflected in the balance of several sets of metabolites (e.g., lactate and pyruvate, beta-hydroxybutyrate and acetoacetate), whose interconversion is dependent on these ratios. Redox mechanisms also control some cellular processes. Redox proteins and their genes must be co-located for redox regulation according to the CoRR hypothesis for the function of DNA in mitochondria and chloroplasts.

4.2 Corrosion and rusting

Oxides, such as iron(III) oxide or rust, which consists of hydrated iron(III) oxides Fe₂O₃·nH₂O and iron(III) oxide-hydroxide (FeO(OH), Fe(OH)₃), form when oxygen combines with other elements. Iron rusting in pyrite cubes.

- The term corrosion refers to the electrochemical oxidation of metals in reaction with an oxidant such as oxygen. Rusting, the formation of iron oxides, is a well-known example of electrochemical corrosion: it forms as a result of the oxidation of iron metal. Common rust often refers to iron (III) oxide, formed in the following chemical reaction:

- The oxidation of iron(II) to iron(III) by hydrogen peroxide in the presence of an acid:

Here the overall equation involves adding the reduction equation to twice the oxidation equation, so that the electrons cancel:

Thus, one sulfur atom is reduced from +2 to 0, while the other is oxidized from +2 to +4.

4.3 Redox reactions in industry

Cathodic protection is a technique used to control the corrosion of a metal surface by making it the cathode of an electrochemical cell. A simple method of protection connects protected metal to a more easily corroded "sacrificial anode" to act as the anode. The sacrificial metal, instead of the protected metal, then corrodes.

Oxidation is used in a wide variety of industries, such as in the production of cleaning products and oxidizing ammonia to produce nitric acid.

Redox reactions are the foundation of electrochemical cells, which can generate electrical energy or support electrosynthesis. Metal ores often contain metals in oxidized states, such as oxides or sulfides, from which the pure metals are extracted by smelting at high temperatures in the presence of a reducing agent. The process of electroplating uses redox reactions to coat objects with a thin layer of a material, as in chrome-plated automotive parts, silver plating cutlery, galvanization and gold-plated jewelry.

4.4 Redox cycling

Wide varieties of aromatic compounds are enzymatically reduced to form free radicals that contain one more electron than their parent compounds. In general, the electron donor is any of a wide variety of flavoenzymes and their coenzymes. Once formed, these anion free radicals reduce molecular oxygen to superoxide and regenerate the unchanged parent compound. The net reaction is the oxidation of the flavoenzyme's coenzymes and the reduction of molecular oxygen to form superoxide. This catalytic behavior has been described as a futile cycle or redox cycling.

Minerals are generally oxidized derivatives of metals. Iron is mined as ores such as magnetite (Fe₃O₄) and hematite (Fe₂O₃). Titanium is mined as its dioxide, usually in the form of rutile (TiO₂). These oxides must be reduced to obtain the corresponding metals, often achieved by heating these oxides with carbon or carbon monoxide as reducing agents. Blast furnaces are the reactors where iron oxides and coke (a form of carbon) are combined to produce molten iron. The main chemical reaction producing the molten iron is:

4.5 Redox reactions in soils

Electron transfer reactions are central to myriad processes and properties in soils, and redox potential, quantified as Eh (platinum electrode potential (voltage) relative to the standard hydrogen electrode) or (analogous to pH as - log electron activity), is a master variable, along with pH, that controls and is governed by chemical reactions and biological processes. Early theoretical research with applications to flooded soils and paddy rice production was seminal for subsequent work on thermodynamic aspects of redox and plant root growth in soils. Later work built on this foundation, and expanded it for understanding redox reactions related to heavy metal oxidation state changes, pedogenesis and morphology, organic compound degradation and formation, free radical chemistry, wetland delineation, soil remediation, and various methodological approaches for characterizing the redox status of soils [15].

5. Discussion

The oxidation state in oxidation – reduction reaction relation with velocity of the electromagnetic waves was derived.

The law of oxidation state dependent of the length of the electromegnetic waves was derived.

The law of the oxidation number and reduction number changes with the length of electromagnetic waves was derived and discussed.

The transition of the oxidation state of chemical reaction was stated.

In redox processes, the reductant transfers electrons to the oxidant.

Redox mechanisms which control some cellular reactions have discussed and kinetic model of respiration has derived.

Examples of applications in industry and soil also were discussed.

6. Conclusion

Oxidation as a process in which a substance loses electrons and translate to the other substage was studied. Reduction is a process in which a substance gains electrons. In the chemical reaction the oxidation and reduction processes occur simultaneously.

In this paper the law of the oxidation state change with change of the velocity of the electromagnetic waves was derived, first time in the literature. The velocity of the electromagnetic waves in oxidation-reduction reaction is not constant.

The law of oxidation state changing with length of the electromegnetic waves was derived first time in the literature.

The law of the oxidation number and reduction number changes with the length of electromagnetic waves was derived first time in this paper, in refers the literature.

Redox mechanisms control some cellular processes. In the rusting of iron, the oxidation state of iron atoms increases as the iron converts to an oxide and simultaneously, the oxidation state of oxygen decreases as it accepts electrons.

Examples of applications in industry and soil also were discussed.

Notation

c - concentration, mol / m^3

f - frequency, $1 / s$

k - the chemical specific rate constant, $1 / s$

n_e - number of electrons

n_{OX} - oxidation number

n_{RED} - reduction number

t - time, s

v - velocity, m / s

Greek Symbols

λ - wavelength, m

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